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Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

D7.5 – REBECCA system evaluation and acceptance by patients and health professionals

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BCP	Breast Cancer Patient
BCS	Breast Cancer Survivor
EHR	Electronic Health Records
HC	Healthy Controls
HCP	Health Care Professionals
KI	Karolinska Institutet
pApp	REBECCA Patient App
PCP	Prostate Cancer Patients
PEOU	Perceived Ease of Use
PS	Perceived Security
PT	Perceived Trust
PU	Perceived Usefulness
QoL	Quality of Life
RWD	Real-World Data
SUS	System Usability Scale
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UEQ	User Experience Questionnaire
UEQ-S	User Experience Questionnaire – Short version
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the evaluation of the REBECCA system (patient app and clinical dashboard) from the end-user perspective, based on both internal study results and external stakeholder input. The evaluation aimed to assess usability, satisfaction, and overall acceptability across multiple countries and participant groups, and to explore broader perspectives from key stakeholders.

The internal evaluation was conducted across different work packages/study designs (WP5, WP6, WP7), countries (Spain, Norway, Sweden), and participant groups including patients (breast and prostate cancer), health care professionals (HCP), healthy controls (HC), and breast cancer survivors (BCS). Standardized instruments were used, including the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ), the System Usability Scale (SUS), and tailored project-specific questions based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Framework. Results showed acceptable to good usability, with SUS scores generally within the “acceptable” or “marginally acceptable” range across participant groups. Pragmatic quality dimensions (e.g., efficiency, supportiveness, clarity) were predominantly positive, confirming the system’s functional adequacy. Hedonic quality scores (e.g., stimulation, novelty) were mostly neutral, particularly among HC and BCS, suggesting that the system is functional but not especially engaging. Satisfaction was higher among patients and HCP, while perceived monitoring was more frequently reported in non-clinical groups (HC and BCS). Differences in quality of life (QoL) improvements, with Spanish patients showing the highest gains (100%), highlight the influence of local healthcare context and cultural factors. Lower trust in data reported by Spanish HCPs underscores the need for improved transparency and integration with existing workflows.

An external evaluation, conducted through the REBECCA final stakeholder workshop at the EHMA Conference in Rennes in June 2025, gathered insights from decision-makers, regulators, healthcare professionals, researchers, and patient organizations, complementing the internal findings. The workshop explored challenges and opportunities related to health data use, emphasizing ethical, inclusive, and user-centred approaches. Overall, results from the external stakeholder evaluation suggest broad acceptability of the system, while highlighting practical implementation challenges, particularly for frontline health professionals.

Taken together, the internal and external evaluations confirm that the REBECCA system can be used to monitor patients’ lifestyles and support improved care pathways. They also underline the need for further refinement, with a focus on enhancing user engagement, increasing trust in system outputs, addressing practical implementation challenges, and adapting the system to local contexts.

1 Introduction

The REBECCA project aims to leverage digital solutions to improve the quality of life (QoL) and lifestyle of breast cancer patients (BCP). As part of this effort, the REBECCA mobile application (pApp) and the clinical dashboard were developed to support patients and health care professionals (HCP) in monitoring health, lifestyle, and behavioural information. To ensure that the system meets the needs of its intended users and is both usable and engaging, an evaluation was carried out upon completion of its piloting phase.

The internal evaluation was conducted in Norway and Spain, where the clinical studies were carried out, and in Sweden, where the feasibility study with breast cancer survivors (BCS) took place. Patients/survivors, healthy controls (HC), and HCP assessed the system using evaluation forms, which comprised three components:

1. **The User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ)**, used to assess overall user experience, including attractiveness, efficiency, dependability, stimulation, and novelty. The UEQ contains either 26 or 8 items, depending on the version used, with responses scored on a 1–7 scale (1 = negative/annoying, 7 = positive/enjoyable).
2. **The System Usability Scale (SUS)**, used to measure perceived usability through 10 items rated on a 1–5 scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree), producing a cumulative score as a benchmark of usability.
3. **An adapted version of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)**, including project-specific questions that were designed to capture feedback on aspects of the REBECCA app not addressed by the UEQ or SUS.

This mixed approach ensured both a structured assessment based on validated tools and the collection of targeted insights aligned with project objectives.

All evaluation forms were translated into the respective national languages and administered electronically via REDCap, allowing participants to respond in a secure and accessible way.

The external evaluation was conducted through an evaluation questionnaire (in English) that it was distributed to the different stakeholders during the REBECCA final stakeholder workshop to gather the perspectives from decision-makers, regulators, HCP, researchers, and patient organizations.

1.1 Aim

The aim of this deliverable is to present a comprehensive evaluation of the REBECCA system (patient app and clinical dashboard) from the end-user perspective, drawing on both internal study results and external stakeholder input.

1.2 Intended audience

This public deliverable is intended for health professionals and managers, clinical researchers, policy makers, regulators, patient organisations, and other relevant stakeholders interested in the evaluation and adoption of novel digital monitoring tools – such as the REBECCA 360° – and provides evidence on the usability, acceptability and implementation considerations in research and healthcare.

1.3 Project partners and acronyms

Throughout this deliverable, the following acronyms are used to refer to REBECCA consortium partners.

Acronym	Partner name	Country
AMAZONA	BROSTCANCERFORENINGEN AMAZONA I STOCKHOLMS LAN	Sweden
EHMA	EUROPEAN HEALTH MANAGEMENT ASSOCIATION	Belgium
INCLIVA	FUNDACION PARA LA INVESTIGACION DEL HOSPITAL CLINICO DE LA COMUNITAT VALENCIANA, FUNDACION INCLIVA	Spain
KI	KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET	Sweden
SUH	HELSE STAVANGER HF	Norway

1.4 Methodology

For the **internal** assessment, evaluation forms were developed by Karolinska Institutet (KI) in REDCap and distributed to the participating sites for translation into the respective national languages. The evaluation was conducted at the end, once each participant had completed their involvement in the study. Upon completion, each clinical site securely sent the REDCap-collected data, encrypted, to KI for analysis.

Data analysis was performed between May and September 2025, using the latest available data. It should be noted that, at the time of preparing the evaluation analysis, the two intervention studies (WP6) were still ongoing in Norway and Spain, and since patient evaluations are collected at study exit, some input could not yet be included. Input from the other four studies, however, is complete.

The analysis of the evaluation forms included standard scoring procedures for validated instruments such as the SUS and the UEQ as well as descriptive statistics (percentages) for the additional questions included in the form.

Overall, the internal evaluation encompassed the following participant groups and studies.

Study	Country / WP	Type	Evaluation Group(s)
<i>REBECCA-OST</i>	Spain WP5	Observational study with a focus on adjuvant-treatment induced osteopenia/osteoporosis	BCP
<i>REBECCA-CRF</i>	Norway WP5	Observational study with a focus on breast cancer-related fatigue	BCP and HC
<i>REBECCA-INCLIVA-Inter-QoL</i>	Spain WP6	Intervention study: REBECCA as an intervention in Valencia	BCP and HCP
<i>REBECCA-SUH-Inter-QoL</i>	Norway WP6	Intervention study: REBECCA as an intervention in Stavanger	BCP and HCP
<i>REBECCA-KI-Feas-QoL</i>	Sweden WP6	Feasibility study: REBECCA for personalized lifestyle counselling in Stockholm	BCS
<i>REBECCA-PROST</i>	Norway WP7	Extension of REBECCA monitoring to male prostate cancer patients (PCP)	PCP

For the **external** evaluation, the External Expert System Evaluation questionnaire was developed by KI and it was distributed in printed form to stakeholders attending the final REBECCA workshop at the EHMA 2025 conference. After the conference, EHMA transferred the responses from paper to an Excel file and send it to KI for analysis.

Average scores (on a 1–7 scale, from “Not at all” to “Extremely”) were calculated for each stakeholder group based on responses to the External Expert System Evaluation. Results were visualized using a grouped bar chart.

The evaluation encompassed the following stakeholder groups:

- Decision/Policy - makers
- Health authorities and regulatory bodies
- Health professionals and health managers
- Researchers and tech innovators
- Students

1.5 Organization of the document

The rest of the document is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the system evaluation framework and provides a detailed description of the evaluation instruments employed in the internal evaluation, including the UEQ, SUS, and TAM. Section 3 presents the results from WP5, detailing the evaluation conducted in Spain and Norway, including BCP and HC assessments. Section 4 focuses on the system evaluation from WP6, covering both Spain and Norway, and the feasibility study in Sweden (REBECCA-KI-Feas-QoL). This section includes evaluations from BCP, BCS and HCP. Section 5 presents the system evaluation from WP7 in Norway, which involved PCP. Section 6 summarises the results from the internal evaluation (presented in Section 4 & 5), while Section 7 presents the external evaluation results, highlighting key insights from all stakeholder groups attending the final stakeholder workshop. The appendices contain the evaluation forms and the minutes from the final stakeholder workshop.

2 System evaluation tools

2.1 Evaluation framework

The evaluation framework used in the REBECCA project is a combination of three components, i.e., (i) User Experience Questionnaire³ (UEQ), (ii) the System Usability Scale⁴ (SUS) and (iii) an adapted version with items from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The evaluation of the REBECCA system’s acceptance, functionality, usability, and satisfaction was conducted using evaluation forms.

2.1.1 The User Experience Questionnaire

The UEQ is a standardized questionnaire used to evaluate the user experience of interactive products. As introduced in 2005, UEQ consists of six scales, each describing a distinct quality aspect of an interactive product, namely: **Attractiveness**, **Perspicuity**, **Efficiency**, **Dependability**, **Stimulation**, and **Novelty**. The UEQ was constructed using a data analytical approach to ensure practical relevance of the constructed scales. The final version includes 26 items (Figure 1) which were extracted from a much larger initial pool of items using principal component analysis and is available (and standardised) in more than 30 languages, including all the study-specific languages in the REBECCA project.

Figure 1. UEQ scales and an illustrative example of the aggregated results across the six outcome scales.

³ Schrepp, M., Hinderks, A., & Thomaschewski, J. (2017). User Experience Questionnaire Handbook. Available online: <https://www.ueq-online.org>

⁴ Brooke, J. (2013). SUS: A retrospective. Journal of Usability Studies, 8(2), 29–40.

A short version of the UEQ (UEQ-S) is also available, containing 8 items that cover the same six quality dimensions while reducing respondent burden, making it particularly suitable for studies where questionnaire length must be minimized.

Figure 2. UEQ-Short item structure and an illustrative example for a benchmark comparison of pragmatic, hedonic, and overall quality

In both the full and short versions, responses are given on a 7-point semantic differential scale, with opposing adjectives placed at each end (e.g., “complicated” vs. “easy”). Scores for each scale are calculated by averaging the corresponding item ratings, resulting in values ranging from -3 (most negative) to +3 (most positive).

According to the UEQ benchmark, values:

- above +0.8 are considered positive
- values between -0.8 and +0.8 are neutral, and
- values below -0.8 are leading negative.

The analysis also allows for comparison against an international benchmark database, classifying results into categories such as “excellent,” “good,” “above average,” “below average,” or “poor” for each dimension.

2.1.2 The System Usability Scale

The SUS is a widely used, reliable tool for assessing the perceived usability of a system. It consists of 10 statements rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from “Strongly disagree” to “Strongly agree,” with items alternating between positive and negative phrasing to minimize response bias.

To calculate the SUS score, responses are converted to numerical values (0–4), adjusted for positive or negative items, summed, and multiplied by 2.5 to yield a score ranging from 0 to 100. While not a percentage, this score reflects overall usability, with 68 considered the benchmark for “average” usability. Scores above 68 are generally interpreted as above average, whereas scores below this threshold may indicate usability issues. In addition to absolute values, results can be interpreted using adjective ratings such as “good,” “excellent,” “poor” (Figure 3).

Figure 3. SUS Items and Scoring Interpretation for Assessing System Usability

2.1.3 The Technology Acceptance Model

TAM was first conceptualized by Fred Davis in the 1980s and stands as a pivotal tool in elucidating how individuals make decisions regarding the adoption of new technology. TAM originated from the domain of information systems research, specifically emerging in the late 1980s and early 1990s, as it was initially developed by Fred Davis in 1986 and was later extended by Davis in collaboration with Richard Bagozzi in 1989. TAM aimed to provide insights into the factors influencing individuals’ acceptance and adoption of new information technologies, especially concerning the potential adoption of new technology-based systems within existing operational frameworks (i.e., close to the goal of the REBECCA system evaluation).⁵

The foundational premise of TAM is that perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) are critical determinants of an individual’s intention to use a technology, which, in turn, influences the actual usage. PU refers to the user’s belief that a particular technology will enhance one’s performance, productivity, or enjoyment while performing a technology-assisted task. On the other hand, PEOU refers to the user’s perception about the ease of the technology use. Currently TAM and various adapted versions of it relevant to specific deployment requirements, much like in the case of REBECCA is widely used in academia, industry, in policymaking and as well as in the health domain. The appropriate uses of TAM, in general, include user-centric evaluations for understanding and predicting user behaviour in adopting a wide range of technologies, from mobile applications to social media platforms and artificial

⁵ Marangunić N, Granić A. Technology acceptance model: a literature review from 1986 to 2013. Universal access in the information society. 2015 Mar;14:81-95.

intelligence.¹ Similarly, in the domain of Health, TAM has previously been used for investigating the acceptance of various technologies, such as electronic health records (EHRs), remote sensing, wearable health devices, and mobile health applications, both by patients and by involved health professionals.⁶

In order to better fit the needs of the REBECCA project, a modified version of TAM⁷ is used (Figure 4), proposed for health-related users' acceptance of m-health services. This modified TAM incorporates key factors including Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Security, and Perceived Trust. These dimensions were chosen to comprehensively assess the medical experts' and patients' viewpoints on the REBECCA system.

In this adaptation of the TAM evaluation the term "**Perceived Usefulness**" delves into the extent to which users believe that the REBECCA system aids them in achieving their objectives, such as enhancing QoL (patients), decision making process (medical experts) and provided treatment (both). It essentially gauges the practical benefits perceived by the users. Additionally, the term "**Perceived Ease of Use**" focuses on the degree to which individuals believe that using the system would be effortless and straightforward. This aspect investigates the system's user-friendliness, which is crucial for widespread acceptance and adoption. Furthermore, "**Perceived Security**" assesses the users' confidence in the system's ability to safeguard their sensitive information and maintain their privacy, a paramount concept in the field of medical technology, as patients' data security is critical in practice, and so is the perception of personal data security by the patients themselves. Finally, the "**Perceived Trust**" evaluation component delves into the users' confidence and faith in the reliability, integrity, and competence of the REBECCA system to perform the described/communicated goals. The perceived trust that the user experiences during the use of the system is a fundamental component in cultivating and sustaining a positive user experience, fostering long-term relationships, and encouraging sustained and long-term usage of the technology.

⁶ AlQudah AA, Al-Emran M, Shaalan K. Technology acceptance in healthcare: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences*. 2021 Nov 9;11(22):10537.

⁷ Alloghani M, Hussain A, Al-Jumeily D, Abuelma'atti O. Technology Acceptance Model for the Use of M-Health Services among health related users in UAE. In 2015 International Conference on Developments of E-Systems Engineering (DeSE) 2015 Dec 13 (pp. 213-217). IEEE.

Figure 4. Modified Technology Acceptance Model

2.2 Evaluation forms

The internal assessment of the final iteration of the REBECCA system was conducted via evaluation forms from the clinical studies in Norway and Spain, as well as from the feasibility study in Sweden. As mentioned above, the evaluation forms consisted of three sections: the UEQ, the SUS, and additional project-specific questions based on the TAM (Figure 5). They were electronically created and distributed through REDCap, translated into the respective national languages, and administered to patients, HC at the study exit, and to HCP at the end of the study. The complete evaluation forms are provided in Annex A.

Figure 5. An example of the integrated version of the patient evaluation for WP6, created in REDCap

3 System evaluation from WP5

3.1 Spain – REBECCA-OST

During the observational study in Spain, the system was evaluated through the UEQ long form, and the evaluation was conducted at two time points: 6 months and 12 months (Figure 6).

Figure 6. System evaluation WP5 - Spain

3.1.1 Long UEQ Results at 6 months

At 6 months after study’s onset, seventy-three BCP were given the Long UEQ form and from those 48 were included in the analysis (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Flow chart of responses analysed at 6 months – Spain, WP5

***Inconsistences:** Each scale (group of questions) should measure the same thing. If a person gives very different answers within the same scale (for example, both very positive and very negative), this is a sign the answers might not be reliable. If this happened on **three or more scales**, that person’s responses are considered inconsistent and are removed from the analysis.

***Critical length:** Identifies cases where participants provide the same response to a large number of items, which may indicate disengagement (e.g., choosing the middle category for nearly all items). Based on

empirical findings across several UEQ datasets, responses in which more than 15 items have identical ratings are flagged under this criterion and also excluded from the analysis.

Table 1 below presents the results of the Long UEQ used to evaluate the system at 6 months. It shows the mean value, variance and standard deviation for each of the 26 scales rated. The "Left" and "Right" columns show the two extremes of the scale (e.g., *annoying* vs. *enjoyable*) participants used to evaluate each aspect of the app. These scales are further grouped into the six overarching dimensions (shown with different colours on the right side of the table): Attractiveness, Perspicuity, Efficiency, Dependability, Stimulation, and Novelty.

Table 1. Overview of UEQ Ratings at 6 months – Spain, BCP, WP5, n=48, 6 months

Item	Mean	Variance	Std. Dev.	No.	Left	Right	Scale
1	2.0	1.4	1.2	48	annoying	enjoyable	Attractiveness
2	-2.5	1.2	1.1	48	not understandable	understandable	Perspicuity
3	1.1	2.3	1.5	47	creative	dull	Novelty
4	2.6	0.8	0.9	48	easy to learn	difficult to learn	Perspicuity
5	2.0	1.7	1.3	44	valuable	inferior	Stimulation
6	0.5	1.4	1.2	44	boring	exciting	Stimulation
7	1.5	1.8	1.4	44	not interesting	interesting	Stimulation
8	1.2	2.2	1.5	44	unpredictable	predictable	Dependability
9	1.5	2.7	1.6	44	fast	slow	Efficiency
10	-0.4	2.3	1.5	44	inventive	conventional	Novelty
11	1.8	1.3	1.1	45	obstructive	supportive	Dependability
12	1.7	2.2	1.5	45	good	bad	Attractiveness
13	2.4	1.4	1.2	45	complicated	easy	Perspicuity
14	2.0	1.0	1.0	45	unlikable	pleasing	Attractiveness
15	-0.3	2.7	1.7	44	usual	leading edge	Novelty
16	2.0	1.2	1.1	45	unpleasant	pleasant	Attractiveness
17	2.1	1.5	1.2	45	secure	not secure	Dependability
18	1.4	2.0	1.4	46	motivating	demotivating	Stimulation
19	1.7	1.4	1.2	46	meets expectations	does not meet expectations	Dependability
20	1.8	1.2	1.1	46	inefficient	efficient	Efficiency
21	2.4	1.4	1.2	46	clear	confusing	Perspicuity
22	1.8	1.9	1.4	46	impractical	practical	Efficiency
23	2.2	1.8	1.3	46	organized	cluttered	Efficiency
24	1.2	1.9	1.4	45	attractive	unattractive	Attractiveness
25	2.0	2.0	1.4	45	friendly	unfriendly	Attractiveness
26	0.3	1.8	1.3	45	conservative	innovative	Novelty

In Figure 8 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 8. Visual Representation of Mean Long UEQ Item Scores – Spain, BCP, WP5, n=48, 6 months

The UEQ results show that most items were rated positively, particularly in the dimensions of Attractiveness, Efficiency, and Dependability, which scored above the neutral range. Perspicuity received mixed ratings, with “not understandable /understandable” falling into the negative area, indicating usability challenges. Stimulation and Novelty were closer/into to the neutral range, suggesting the system was perceived as functional but less exciting or innovative.

3.1.2 Long UEQ Results at 12 months

At 12 months sixty-nine BCPs were given the Long UEQ form and from those 52 were included in the analysis (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Flow chart of responses analysed at 12 months – Spain, BCP WP5

**For a detailed explanation of inconsistencies and critical length, see p. 20*

Table 2. Overview of UEQ Ratings – Spain, BCP, WP5, n=52, 12 months

Item	Mean	Variance	Std. Dev.	No.	Left	Right	Scale
1	1.4	1.6	1.3	52	annoying	enjoyable	Attractiveness
2	-1.8	3.1	1.8	52	not understandable	understandable	Perspiciuity
3	0.7	2.0	1.4	52	creative	dull	Novelty
4	2.2	2.0	1.4	52	easy to learn	difficult to learn	Perspiciuity
5	1.5	2.3	1.5	51	valuable	inferior	Stimulation
6	0.1	1.8	1.3	52	boring	exciting	Stimulation
7	1.2	1.3	1.2	52	not interesting	interesting	Stimulation
8	1.1	1.7	1.3	52	unpredictable	predictable	Dependability
9	0.8	2.9	1.7	52	fast	slow	Efficiency
10	-0.4	1.9	1.4	52	inventive	conventional	Novelty
11	1.0	1.7	1.3	52	obstructive	supportive	Dependability
12	1.6	1.9	1.4	52	good	bad	Attractiveness
13	2.0	2.0	1.4	52	complicated	easy	Perspiciuity
14	1.7	1.4	1.2	51	unlikable	pleasing	Attractiveness
15	-0.4	2.4	1.6	52	usual	leading edge	Novelty
16	1.8	1.4	1.2	52	unpleasant	pleasant	Attractiveness
17	1.5	1.9	1.4	49	secure	not secure	Dependability
18	0.8	1.3	1.1	49	motivating	demotivating	Stimulation
19	1.1	1.7	1.3	50	meets expectations	does not meet expectations	Dependability
20	1.1	1.4	1.2	49	inefficient	efficient	Efficiency
21	2.2	1.2	1.1	50	clear	confusing	Perspiciuity
22	1.2	2.1	1.4	50	impractical	practical	Efficiency
23	2.1	1.4	1.2	50	organized	cluttered	Efficiency
24	0.8	1.9	1.4	50	attractive	unattractive	Attractiveness
25	1.8	1.5	1.2	49	friendly	unfriendly	Attractiveness
26	-0.2	2.1	1.4	48	conservative	innovative	Novelty

In Figure 10 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the center marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 10. Visual Representation of Mean Long UEQ Item Scores - Spain, BCP, WP5, n=52, 12 months

The UEQ results indicate overall positive ratings across most dimensions, with Attractiveness, Efficiency, and Dependability scoring above neutral. Perspicuity showed variability, with “not understandable/understandable” rated negatively, highlighting potential clarity issues. Stimulation and Novelty remained close to neutral, suggesting limited perceived excitement or innovation.

3.1.2.1 Comparison of UEQ results 6 months vs 12 months

In both evaluations, Attractiveness, Efficiency, and Dependability were consistently rated positively. Stimulation shifted from positive to the neutral range, while Novelty remained in the neutral range. Perspicuity was the weakest scale among the positively rated scales in both cases, driven mainly by low scores for “not understandable /understandable.” However, the user experience ratings decreased in all categories, reflecting a less positive perception of the system over time.

Table 3. Comparison of UEQ results (6 months vs 12 months) – Spain, WP5

Scale	6-Month Mean (N=48)	12-Month Mean (N=52)	Change
Attractiveness	1.783	1.510	▼ 0.273
Perspicuity	1.160	1.115	▼ 0.045
Efficiency	1.703	1.295	▼ 0.408
Dependability	1.722	1.173	▼ 0.549
Stimulation	1.326	0.875	▼ 0.451
Novelty	0.206	-0.061	▼ 0.267

3.2 Norway – REBECCA-CRF

The observational study in Norway (REBECCA-CRF) ran from September 2022 to June 2025. The system evaluation was conducted 12 or 18 months after the start of the study and involved both BCP and HC. It included the UEQ-S, the SUS, and additional project-specific questions. Of the forty-one BCP who participated, thirty completed the evaluation form, and among the forty-three HC, thirty-seven evaluated the system.

Figure 11. System evaluation WP5 - Norway

3.2.1 BCP evaluation of the pApp

3.2.1.1 UEQ-S

To evaluate the user experience of the pApp, the UEQ-S was used, which consists of 8 items rated on a 7-point semantic differential scale, with opposing adjectives placed at each end (e.g., "complicated" vs. "easy"). The "Negative" and "Positive" columns show the two extremes of the scale participants used to evaluate each aspect of the pApp. Table 4 shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated. These items are grouped into two broader dimensions of user experience: Pragmatic Quality and Hedonic Quality. Pragmatic Quality refers to how useful, easy to use, and clear the app is, while Hedonic Quality reflects how engaging, exciting, and interesting the app feels.

Table 4. Overview of UEQ Ratings - Norway, BCP WP5, n=30

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	1.0	1.5	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	1.4	1.7	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	0.4	1.8	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	0.9	1.6	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	0.3	1.8	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	0.7	1.6	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	0.6	1.5	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	0.4	1.7	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

In Figure 12 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 12. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores – Norway, BCP WP5, n=30

As seen in the results, supportiveness, ease of use, and clarity were rated positively, standing out as strengths of the system. The other pragmatic quality (efficiency) and all hedonic qualities (excitement, interest, inventiveness, innovativeness) received more moderate scores, falling within the neutral range. This suggests that while the system was perceived as functional and easy to use, it was viewed as moderately engaging or innovative from an experiential perspective.

3.2.1.2 SUS Questionnaire

The SUS questionnaire was administered to evaluate the usability of the app among the participants. The SUS consists of 10 standardized questions that assess users perceived ease of use, complexity, and overall satisfaction with a system. Responses are scored on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, which are then converted into a total score between 0 and 100.

Twenty-one BCP completed the questionnaire, of whom 2 responses were excluded due to incomplete data, resulting in 19 valid responses for analysis. The average SUS score obtained was 65, which falls within the range of marginally acceptable usability (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Mean SUS score – Norway, WP5 BCP, n=19

3.2.1.3 Additional questions

In addition to the standardized questionnaires, participants were asked a set of additional questions to gain further insights into their experiences with the REBECCA system. These questions were administered to gather information on aspects such as perceived usefulness, satisfaction, and data privacy.

Figure 14 shows participants' perceptions of whether using the app improved their QoL. A majority (around 65%) reported that the app did not improve their QoL, while approximately one-quarter (25%) were unsure, and a small proportion (10%) felt it had a positive impact. However, it is important to note that these findings stem from an observational study rather than an intervention, and that the app was not in its final state during this study for all participants, which further limits the ability to draw definitive conclusions.

Figure 14. Perceived potential of the pApp to enhance QoL after primary treatment, Norway, BCP WP5, n=28

The following figure (Figure 15) illustrates participants’ feelings about privacy when using the app. Most participants felt secure (about 37%) or very secure (around 56%), while only a small minority reported feeling insecure or very insecure, or were unsure.

Figure 15. Feelings about privacy - Norway, BCP WP5, n=27

Figure 16 reflects whether participants felt monitored while using the app. The majority (around 70%) reported that they did not feel monitored, while about 30% said they had not thought about it, and none of the participants reported actively feeling monitored.

Figure 16. Perception of being monitored - Norway, BCP WP5, n=27

The last figure (Figure 17) presents overall satisfaction with the pApp. Most participants were satisfied (about 37%) or very satisfied (30%), while around 22% felt neutral and a smaller proportion (11%) expressed dissatisfaction. No participants reported being very dissatisfied.

Figure 17. Overall satisfaction - Norway, BCP WP5, n=27

3.2.2 HC evaluation of the pApp

3.2.2.1 UEQ-S

Thirty-seven HC evaluated the pApp using the UEQ-S. One participant was excluded for providing identical responses across all categories, leaving 36 for analysis. The Table 5 below shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated.

Table 5. Overview of UEQ Ratings - Norway, HC WP5, n=36

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	0.4	1.5	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	1.1	1.6	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	-0.1	1.6	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	0.7	1.5	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	-0.2	1.4	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	0.1	1.6	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	0.0	1.3	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	-0.3	1.2	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

Figure 18 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided.

Figure 18. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores – Norway, HC WP5, n=36

Values between -0.8 and 0.8 represent a neutral evaluation

Values > 0,8 represent a positive evaluation

Values < -0,8 represent a negative evaluation

As seen in the results, the ease of use was the only quality that was evaluated positively. The rest of the pragmatic qualities (supportive, clear, efficient) as well as the hedonic qualities, reflecting how exciting, interesting, inventive, or innovative the system felt to users, received more moderate ratings, falling into to the neutral range.

3.2.2.2 SUS Questionnaire

Thirty-six HC completed the questionnaire, of whom 4 responses were excluded due to incomplete or invalid data, resulting in 32 valid responses for analysis. The average SUS score obtained was 58, which falls within the range of marginally acceptable usability (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Mean SUS score – Norway, HC, WP5 n=32

3.2.2.3 Additional questions

When HC were asked whether they felt the REBECCA pApp enhance their QoL over half of participants responded, "I don't know", while around 40% answered "No" and only a very small proportion said "Yes." These results should be interpreted with caution, given the observational nature of the study, in which no intervention was implemented and the development stage of the pApp. Additionally, for HC – who are healthy and not cancer patients – it is probably even more difficult to imagine potential improvements in their QoL.

Figure 20. Perceived potential of the pApp to enhance QoL after primary treatment, Norway, HC WP5, n=37

Most participants reported feeling secure or very secure about their privacy while using the pApp, with nearly half selecting “Very Secure” and over one-third selecting “Secure”. Only a small percentage felt insecure, and around 14% were uncertain. These results suggest a generally high level of trust in the pApp’s privacy measures.

Figure 21. Feelings about privacy - Norway, HC WP5, n=36

Most participants (68%) reported that they did not feel monitored while using the pApp. A smaller proportion (16%) felt monitored, while another 16% indicated they had not thought about it. This suggests that the majority of users were comfortable with the pApp’s level of oversight, though a small subset did perceive a sense of monitoring.

Figure 22. Perception of being monitored - Norway, HC WP5, n=37

Overall satisfaction with the pApp was mixed. While nearly half of participants reported being “Satisfied” or “Very Satisfied” (46%), about one-fifth expressed dissatisfaction (20%). The largest group (34%) remained neutral, suggesting that although many participants had a positive experience, there is room for improvement to increase engagement and reduce ambivalence.

Figure 23. Overall satisfaction - Norway, HC WP5, n=35

3.2.3 BCP vs HC Evaluation

3.2.3.1 UEQ Evaluation

Figure 24 illustrates a comparative analysis of mean item values between the BCP and HC. Both groups rated the pragmatic quality of the pApp higher compared to the hedonic. Notably, BCP demonstrate higher means in all the item rated and evaluated positively 3 out of the 4 items in the pragmatic quality compared to 1 out of 4 of the HC. These findings reflect differing ways participants experienced the pApp and that might be because BCP who were more likely to benefit from the pApp, appeared more optimistic compared to the HC.

Figure 24. UEQ mean values BCP vs HC, WP5, Norway

3.2.3.2 SUS Evaluation

BCP provided higher ratings for the pApp on the SUS compared to HC. However, both groups' scores fell within the range of marginally acceptable usability.

Figure 25. SUS score BCP vs HC, WP5, Norway

3.2.3.3 Additional questions

The figures below present a comparison of responses from BCP and HC to a selection of the additional questions administered at 12 months of the observational study. As this was an observation study, the results should be interpreted with caution.

Figure 26 shows perceptions of whether the pApp improved QoL. Most participants in both groups reported no improvement with a higher percentage of BCP. A larger proportion of HC (around 55%) selected "I don't know," compared to about one-quarter of BCP, while only a small percentage of both groups perceived a positive impact.

Figure 26. QoL Improvement, BCP vs HC, WP5, Norway

Figure 27 illustrates feelings about privacy. Both groups reported high levels of confidence, with over 80% of participants indicating that they felt secure or very secure. Very few participants felt insecure or very insecure, and uncertainty was more common among HC than BCP.

Figure 27. Feelings about privacy, BCP vs HC, WP5, Norway

Figure 28 reflects whether participants felt monitored while using the pApp. The majority of both groups (around 70%) stated that they did not feel monitored. A small proportion of HC (around 15%) reported feeling monitored, while nearly one-third of BCP said they had not thought about it.

Figure 28. Felt monitored, BCP vs HC, WP5, Norway

The fourth figure presents overall satisfaction. Satisfaction levels were relatively high in both groups (higher in BCP group), with the majority reporting being satisfied or very satisfied. Neutral responses were more common among HC, while dissatisfaction remained low in both groups, and only a few HC reported being very dissatisfied.

Figure 29. Overall Satisfaction, BCP vs HC, WP5, Norway

Overall, BCP and HC reported similar perceptions of privacy with low levels of discomfort or perceived monitoring. However, HC tended to be less satisfied and more uncertain about potential QoL benefits. In general, HC appeared more cautious and

less enthusiastic in their responses compared to BCP, with a higher frequency of “I don’t know,” “Neutral,” and occasional “Very dissatisfied” ratings. This difference likely stems from HC limited personal connection to the challenges of illness. Without firsthand experience of the pApp’s intended support, they may find it harder to recognize clear benefits, which can result in a more critical or emotionally detached evaluation.

4 System evaluation from WP6

4.1 Spain - REBECCA-INCLIVA-Inter-QoL

The system's evaluation in the intervention study in Spain, involves both BCP and HCP. It includes the UEQ-S, the SUS, and additional project-specific questions. At the time of writing this report, fifteen BCP and five HCP had completed the evaluation form.

Figure 30. System evaluation WP6 - Spain

4.1.1 BCP evaluation of the pApp

4.1.1.1 UEQ-S

Fifteen BCP evaluated the pApp using the UEQ-S. Table 6 shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated. All items received positive ratings, with mean values above 0.8. Pragmatic qualities such as clarity, ease of use, supportiveness, and efficiency were consistently well-evaluated, confirming that the system is perceived as functional and user-friendly. Hedonic qualities, including excitement, inventiveness, and innovativeness, were also rated positively, suggesting that participants found the system engaging and stimulating overall.

Table 6. Overview of UEQ Ratings –Spain, BCP WP6, n=15

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	1.8	1.4	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	2.3	1.5	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	1.5	1.7	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	2.0	2.1	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	1.0	1.6	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	1.4	1.6	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	1.9	1.4	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	1.6	1.4	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

In Figure 31 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation

Figure 31. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores - Spain, BCP WP6, n=15

4.1.1.2 SUS Questionnaire

Fifteen BCP completed the questionnaire. The average SUS score obtained was 74.5, which falls within the range of acceptable usability (Figure 32).

Figure 32. Mean SUS score – Spain, BCP WP6, n=15

4.1.1.3 Additional questions

Figure 33 illustrates BCP perceptions of whether the pApp improved their QoL.

Figure 33. Perceived QoL improvement after primary treatment, Spain, BCP WP6, n= 15

The following figure presents BCP feelings about privacy when using the pApp and the wearable.

Figure 34. Feelings about privacy, Spain, BCP WP6, n= 15

Figure 35 illustrates participants’ perceptions of whether they felt monitored while using the pApp and the wearable. Encouragingly, none of the BCP reported feeling monitored.

Figure 35. Felt monitored. Spain, BCP WP6, n= 13

Figure 36 presents BCP overall satisfaction levels. Most respondents reported positive experiences, with 80% being satisfied (47% very satisfied and 33% satisfied) The remaining 20% were neutral, and none reported dissatisfaction.

Figure 36. Overall satisfaction, Spain, BCP WP6, n= 15

4.1.2 HCP evaluation of the system

4.1.2.1 UEQ-S

Five HCP completed the evaluation, and as shown in Table 7, all items received positive ratings, with mean values above 0.8. Pragmatic qualities were consistently well-evaluated, confirming that the system is perceived as functional and user-friendly. Hedonic qualities, including excitement, interest and inventiveness, were rated positively, while innovativeness was on the borderline between neutral and positive.

Table 7. Overview of UEQ Ratings - Spain, HCP WP6, n=5

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	2.0	0.7	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	1.8	0.8	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	1.8	0.8	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	1.8	0.8	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	1.2	1.5	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	1.8	1.1	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	1.0	1.0	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	0.8	0.8	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

*Ratings from 1 to 7

In Figure 37 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 37. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores - Spain, HCP WP6, n=5

4.1.2.2 SUS Questionnaire

Five HCP completed the SUS questionnaire. The average SUS score obtained was 56.5, which falls within the range of marginal acceptable usability (Figure 38).

Figure 38. Mean SUS score – Spain, HCP WP6 n=5

4.1.2.3 Additional questions

To complement the standardized questionnaires, HCP were asked targeted questions to assess their experience with the REBECCA system (Annex A.3). The following tables summarize their responses.

HCP were asked whether they felt the REBECCA system was integrated into their clinical workflow.

Table 8. Perceived integration of the REBECCA system into clinical workflow - Spain, HCP WP6, n=5

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Yes	4	80%
No	1	20%

The following question evaluated whether the clinical dashboard supported HCP in enhancing their workflow.

Table 9. Usefulness of the clinical dashboard in improving workflow - Spain, HCP WP6, n=5

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Yes	2	40%
No	3	60%

HCP rated also their level of trust in the pApp's data for monitoring patients' lifestyles.

Table 10. Trust in pApp data for monitoring patient lifestyles - Spain, HCP WP6, n=5

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Not at all	0	0%
A little	2	40%
Moderately	1	20%
A lot	2	40%
Extremely	0	0%

The following question captured HCP overall satisfaction with using the REBECCA system.

Table 11. Overall satisfaction with the REBECCA system experience - Spain, HCP WP6, n=5

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Very satisfied	5	100%
Satisfied	0	0%
Neutral	0	0%
Dissatisfied	0	0%
Very dissatisfied	0	0%

4.2 Norway - REBECCA-SUH-Inter-QoL

The intervention study in Norway (REBECCA-SUH-Inter-QoL) ran from July 2023 and will conclude in December 2025. The system’s evaluation is being conducted 12 or 18 months after the start of the study and involves both BCP and HCP. It includes the UEQ-S, the SUS, and additional project-specific questions. At the time of writing this report, twenty-eight BCP have completed the evaluation form, and three HCP.

Figure 39. System evaluation WP6 - Norway

4.2.1 BCP evaluation of the pApp

4.2.1.1 UEQ-S

Twenty-eight BCP evaluated the pApp using the UEQ-S. Table 12 shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated. Each of the 8 items, represents a bipolar adjective pair (e.g., obstructive–supportive), rated on a 7-point scale from -3 to +3.

Table 12. Overview of UEQ Ratings - Norway, BCP WP6, n=28

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	1.1	1.4	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	2.1	1.2	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	0.6	2.1	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	1.5	1.6	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	0.3	1.9	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	0.6	1.9	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	0.3	1.8	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	-0.3	2.0	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

**Evaluation from 1 to 7*

In Figure 40 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 40. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores - Norway, BCP WP6, n=28

As seen in the results, supportiveness, ease of use, and clarity were rated positively, standing out as strengths of the system. The other pragmatic quality (efficiency) and all hedonic qualities (excitement, interest, inventiveness, innovativeness) received more moderate scores, falling within the neutral range. This suggests that while the system was perceived as functional and easy to use, it was viewed as moderately engaging or innovative from an experiential perspective.

4.2.1.2 SUS Questionnaire

Twenty-eight BCP completed the questionnaire, of whom five responses were excluded due to incomplete data, resulting in twenty-three valid responses for analysis. The average SUS score obtained was 71.7, which falls within the range of acceptable usability (Figure 41).

Figure 41. Mean SUS score – Norway, BCP, WP6 n=23

4.2.1.3 Additional questions

Figure 42 illustrates BCP perceptions of whether the pApp improved their QoL. Over half (around 55%) reported that the pApp did not improve their QoL, while about one-third (35%) felt it had a positive effect. A smaller proportion (approximately 10%) were uncertain.

Figure 42. Perceived QoL improvement after primary treatment, Norway, BCP WP6, n= 26

The following figure (Figure 43) presents BCP feelings about privacy when using the pApp. The majority expressed positive views, with around half (50%) reporting that they felt secure and more than one-third (35%) feeling very secure. Only a small proportion indicated negative perceptions, with about 10% reporting that they felt very insecure and a few participants (under 5%) stating they felt insecure.

Figure 43. Feelings about privacy, Norway, BCP WP6, n = 28

Figure 44 shows participants' perceptions of whether they felt monitored while using the pApp. The vast majority (79%) reported that they did not feel monitored, while about 15% stated that they had not thought about it. Only a very small proportion (around 7%) indicated that they did feel monitored. These results suggest that most participants did not experience the pApp as intrusive.

Figure 44. Felt monitored. Norway, BCP WP6, n= 28

Most participants were satisfied (about 75% combined "Satisfied" and "Very satisfied"), while only around 15% expressed dissatisfaction. These findings suggest a generally positive experience.

Figure 45. Overall satisfaction. Norway, BCP WP6, n= 26

4.2.2 HCP evaluation of the system

4.2.2.1 UEQ-S

Three HCP evaluated the REBECCA system using the UEQ-S. The Table 13 below shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated.

Table 13. Overview of UEQ Ratings - Norway, HCP WP6, n=3

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	1.7	0.6	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	2.0	0.0	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	1.0	1.0	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	1.7	0.6	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	2.0	1.0	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	2.3	0.6	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	1.0	1.0	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	0.7	1.2	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

*Evaluation from 1 to 7

Figure 46 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided.

Figure 46. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores – Norway, HCP WP6, n=3

Values between -0.8 and 0.8 represent a neutral evaluation

Values > 0,8 represent a positive evaluation

Values < -0,8 represent a negative evaluation

4.2.2.2 SUS Questionnaire

Three HCP completed the SUS questionnaire. The average SUS score obtained was 78.3, which falls within the range of acceptable usability (Figure 47).

Figure 47. Mean SUS score – Norway, HCP, WP6 n=3

4.2.2.3 Additional questions

To complement the standardized questionnaires, HCP were asked targeted questions to assess their experience with the REBECCA system (Annex A.3). The following tables summarize their responses (n = 3).

HCP were asked whether they felt the REBECCA system was integrated into their clinical workflow.

Table 14. Perceived integration of the REBECCA system into clinical workflow - Norway, HCP WP6, n=2

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Yes	2	100%
No	0	

The following question evaluated whether the clinical dashboard supported HCP in enhancing their workflow.

Table 15. Usefulness of the clinical dashboard in improving workflow - Norway, HCP WP6, n=2

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Yes	2	100%
No	0	

HCP rated also their level of trust in the pApp's data for monitoring patients' lifestyles.

Table 16. Trust in pApp data for monitoring patient lifestyles - Norway, HCP WP6, n=3

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Not at all	0	0%
A little	0	0%
Moderately	0	0%
A lot	3	100%
Extremely	0	0%

The following question captured HCP overall satisfaction with using the REBECCA system.

Table 17. Overall satisfaction with the REBECCA system experience - Norway, HCP WP6, n=3

Answer	Count (Frequency)	Percentage %
Very satisfied	0	0%
Satisfied	2	67%
Neutral	1	33%
Dissatisfied	0	0%
Very dissatisfied	0	0%

4.3 Sweden - REBECCA-KI-Feas-QoL

The REBECCA-KI-Feas-QoL was conducted in Stockholm by KI in collaboration with AMAZONA. The study evaluated the usability and feasibility of the REBECCA system, as well as changes in BCS QoL, using data collected from the pApp, Garmin wearable devices, browser history, and REDCap questionnaires among BCS. Of the 61 BCS initially enrolled, 54 were included in the final analysis.

4.3.1 Evaluation of the pApp – UEQ-S

To evaluate the user experience of the pApp, the UEQ-S was used, and 55 responses were collected. Two responses were excluded from the analysis: one due to a critical pattern, where inconsistent ratings within the same scale indicated a low-quality response, and one due to critical length, defined as 15 or more identical answers, suggesting low engagement. As a result, 53 responses were included in the final analysis.

Table 18 shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated. The "Negative" and "Positive" columns show the two extremes of the scale participants used to evaluate each aspect of the pApp. These items are grouped into two broader dimensions of user experience: Pragmatic Quality and Hedonic Quality. Pragmatic Quality refers to how useful, easy to use, and clear the pApp is, while Hedonic Quality reflects how engaging, exciting, and interesting the pApp feels.

Table 18. Overview of UEQ, - Sweden, BCS, WP6 n=53

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	0.2	1.3	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	1.8	1.2	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	0.2	1.2	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	1.1	1.5	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	-0.5	1.1	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	0.1	1.4	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	-0.1	1.0	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	0.0	1.0	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

In Figure 48 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 48. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores - Sweden, BCS, WP6, n=53

As seen in Figure 48, the pragmatic qualities of the pApp such as how easy, and clear it is, were evaluated positively. In contrast, the rest of the pragmatic aspects (supportiveness and efficiency) and all the hedonic qualities, which capture how interesting, exciting, or novel the pApp felt to BCS, received neutral ratings. This suggests that while the pApp was seen as functional, it was perceived as emotionally neutral or less engaging in terms of user experience.

4.3.2 Evaluation of the pApp – SUS Questionnaire

Fifty-four participants completed the SUS questionnaire, of whom 3 responses were excluded due to incomplete or invalid data, resulting in 51 valid responses for analysis. The average SUS score obtained was 68.53, which is just around the threshold of acceptable usability. However, scores above 68 are generally considered above average.

Figure 49. SUS Results - Sweden, BCS, WP6, n=51

4.3.3 Evaluation of the consultation

At the end of the study (3 months from baseline), BCS were asked to evaluate the overall value and relevance of the personalized consultations. The questions aimed to capture their perceptions of the usefulness of the content, how well it addressed their individual needs, and whether it had a positive impact on their daily life and well-being. Responses were collected using a 5-point scale ranging from "Not at all" to "Completely". BCS responses are presented in the graphs below.

Around half of the BCS reported that they trusted the guidance provided during the consultation "A lot". A smaller portion expressed complete trust, while very few BCS reported low or no trust.

Figure 50. Trust in the guidance- Sweden, BCS, WP6, n=53

A large portion of the BCS felt that the recommendations aligned well with their personal needs, with many indicating that the guidance provided was relevant and appropriate for their situation. Fewer participants reported only moderate alignment, and very few felt that the recommendations did not meet their needs.

Figure 51. Recommendations' alignment with participants' needs- Sweden, BCS, WP6, n=53

When asked about improvements in their QoL, many BCS reported noticing a slight or moderate positive change. Only a few BCS indicated either a substantial improvement or no improvement at all.

Figure 52. Perceived improvement in QoL- Sweden, BCS, WP6, n=53

5 System evaluation from WP7

5.1 Norway - REBECCA-PROST

The feasibility study in Norway (REBECCA-PROST) conducted in PCP and ran from February 2024 to August 2024. The system’s evaluation includes the UEQ-S, the SUS, and additional project-specific questions.

5.1.1 Evaluation of the pApp – UEQ-S

Twenty-one PCP evaluated the pApp using the UEQ-S. One participant was excluded for providing identical responses across all categories, leaving 20 for analysis. Table 19 shows the mean value and standard deviation for each of the 8 items rated.

Table 19. Overview of UEQ Ratings - Norway, PCP WP7, n=20

Item	Mean	Std. Dev.	Negative	Positive	Scale
1	0.8	1.2	obstructive	supportive	Pragmatic Quality
2	1.5	1.6	complicated	easy	Pragmatic Quality
3	1.1	1.2	inefficient	efficient	Pragmatic Quality
4	1.3	1.2	confusing	clear	Pragmatic Quality
5	0.2	1.0	boring	exciting	Hedonic Quality
6	0.6	1.3	not interesting	interesting	Hedonic Quality
7	0.1	1.1	conventional	inventive	Hedonic Quality
8	0.1	1.1	usual	leading edge	Hedonic Quality

In Figure 53 that follows, a visual representation of these results is provided. The shaded purple area in the centre marks the neutral range, with values between -0.8 and +0.8. Values above +0.8 reflect a positive evaluation, while values below -0.8 indicate a negative evaluation.

Figure 53. Visual Representation of Mean UEQ Item Scores - Norway, PCP WP7, n=20

As seen in the results, supportiveness, ease of use, efficiency and clarity were rated positively. All hedonic qualities (excitement, interest, inventiveness, innovativeness) received more moderate scores, falling within the neutral range.

5.1.2 Evaluation of the pApp – SUS Questionnaire

Twenty-eight PCP completed the questionnaire, of whom five responses were excluded due to incomplete data, resulting in twenty-three valid responses for analysis. The average SUS score obtained was 68.1, which falls within the range of marginal acceptable usability (Figure 54).

Figure 54. Mean SUS score – Norway, PCP, WP7, n=23

5.1.3 Additional questions

In addition to the standardized questionnaires, PCPs were asked a set of additional questions to gain further insights into their experiences with the REBECCA system. Figure 55 illustrates PCP’s perceptions of whether the pApp improved their QoL.

Figure 55. Perceived QoL improvement after primary treatment, Norway, PCP WP7, n= 21

The following figure (Figure 56) presents PCP feelings about privacy when using the pApp. The majority expressed positive views, with around 45% reporting that they felt secure and around 30% feeling very secure.

Figure 56. Feelings about privacy, Norway, PCP WP7, n= 21

Figure 57 shows participants' perceptions of whether they felt monitored while using the pApp. The vast majority (81%) reported that they did not feel monitored, while about 15% stated that they had not thought about it.

Figure 57. Felt monitored. Norway, PCP WP7, n= 21

Lastly, Figure 58 presents the overall satisfaction of PCP. Most participants were satisfied (about 66% combined "Satisfied" and "Very satisfied"), while only around 5% expressed dissatisfaction. These findings suggest a generally positive experience.

Figure 58. Overall satisfaction. Norway, PCP, WP7, n= 18

6 Result summary – internal evaluation

6.1 UEQ results

Table 20 summarizes the UEQ results, showing pragmatic and hedonic quality average scores as well as the overall average scores across the three countries based on the different studies (WPs), and participant groups.

Table 20. UEQ results by country, WP and participants' group

Country	WP	Group	Average score (-3 to +3)		
			Pragmatic Quality	Hedonic Quality	Overall
Norway	WP5	BCP	0.9	0.5	0.7
	WP5	HC	0.5	-0.1	0.2
	WP6	HCP	1.6	1.5	1.5
	WP6	BCP	1.3	0.3	0.8
	WP7	PCP	1.2	0.2	0.7
Spain	WP5	BCP/6m	1.5	0.8	Not available for the long UEQ
	WP5	BCP/12m	1.2	0.4	
	WP6	HCP	1.9	1.2	1.5
	WP6	BCP	1.9	1.5	1.7
Sweden (Feasibility)	WP6	BCS	0.8	0.1	0.37

-0.8 to 0.8: neutral (orange)

> 0.8: positive (green)

Overall, the pragmatic quality (usefulness and efficiency) of the user experience evaluation received positive ratings across nearly all groups, except for HC in Norway (and BCS in Sweden, whose score was just below the threshold for being considered positive). This indicates that most participants found the system functional and supportive for its intended purpose. However, hedonic quality (engagement, excitement, and interest) was rated positively only by HCPs and BCP participating in the intervention study (WP6) in Spain.

Participants in WP5 (observational studies) generally reported lower ratings compared to those in WP6 (intervention studies), which is expected given the nature of the studies and the development stage of the pApp. Across both sites, HCP rated the system more positively than patients, suggesting they considered it beneficial and relevant to clinical practice. In contrast, HC in Norway and BCS in Sweden provided the lowest ratings, possibly because the system was less directly applicable to their needs.

6.2 SUS results

Table 21 presents the SUS scores, indicating the perceived usability of the system across the three countries based on the different studies (WP), and participant groups.

Table 21. SUS results by country, WP and participants' group

Country	WP	Group	SUS Average Score (0 -100)
Norway	WP5	BCP	65
	WP5	HC	58
	WP6	HCP	78.3
	WP6	BCP	71.7
	WP7	PCP	68.13
Spain	WP5	BCP	Not available
	WP5	BCP	Not available
	WP6	HCP	56.5
	WP6	BCP	74.5
Sweden (Feasibility)	WP6	BCS	68.53

52 - 70: *marginal acceptable usability (OK)*

> 70: *acceptable usability*

BCP in the intervention studies (WP6) in both Norway and Spain and HCP in Norway evaluated the REBECCA system with an average SUS score above 70 indicating an acceptable level of usability. Additionally, the two feasibility studies with BCS in Sweden (WP6) and PCP in Norway (WP7) reported average SUS scores above 68, which is generally considered acceptable usability as well. All other groups provided scores within the "marginally acceptable" usability range.

6.3 Additional questions results

The results in Table 22 summarize the answers of patient groups and HC in the following measures: (1) Satisfaction, which reflects the percentage of participants who reported being "Very satisfied" or "Satisfied"; (2) Felt monitored, indicating the proportion of participants who answered "Yes" to feeling monitored while using the pApp and wearing the watch; and (3) QoL improvement represents the percentage of participants who reported a positive ("Yes") change in their QoL. In the Swedish feasibility study, this question was not a simple yes/no format, as QoL improvement was not the primary aim. In this case, the percentage reflects participants who selected positive options ("completely", "a lot", or "moderately").

Table 22. Satisfaction, perceived monitoring, and QoL improvement across patients

Country	WP	Group	Satisfaction	Felt monitored	QoL improvement
Norway	WP5	BCP	67%	0%	11%
	WP5	HC	46%	16%	3%
	WP6	BCP	73%	7%	35%
	WP7	PCP	66%	5%	10%
Spain	WP6	BCP	80%	0%	100%
Sweden (Feasibility)	WP6	BCS	44%	13%	18% (moderately)

As shown in Table 22 overall satisfaction levels were high across most of the groups, with over 65% of participants reporting being satisfied or very satisfied with the system. Satisfaction rates were below 50% only among HC and BCS, likely because the system was less relevant to their needs. These two groups also reported higher feelings of being monitored (16% and 13%) compared to 0–7% in the other groups. Reported QoL improvements varied widely: Spanish patients in the intervention study reported 100% improvement, while the other groups had much lower rates, with the next highest being 35% among BCP in Norway in the intervention study (WP6).

The results in Table 23 summarize four key measures for HCP: (1) Satisfaction: percentage of HCPs who were “Very satisfied” or “Satisfied”; (2) System integration: percentage of HCP who answered “Yes” to successful integration into the clinical workflow; (3) Workflow improvement: percentage of HCP who answered “Yes” to the dashboard improving their workflow; and (4) Trust in data: percentage of HCP who reported trusting the pApp data (“extremely” to “moderately”).

Table 23. HCP Evaluation Results: Norway vs. Spain (WP6)

Evaluation measures	Norway HCP WP6	Spain HCP WP6
Overall satisfaction	67%	100%
Integration of the system in the clinical workflow	100%	80%
Workflow improvement using dashboard	100%	40%
Trust the data collected from the pApp	100%	40%

The Norwegian HCPs were less satisfied with the system compared to the Spanish HCPs. However, only 40% of the Spanish HCPs reported that the clinical dashboard improved their workflow and 60% expressed lower trust in the data, even though the majority (80%) felt that the system was integrated into the clinical workflow.

7 REBECCA final stakeholder workshop – external evaluation

The REBECCA final stakeholder workshop took place on 5th of June 2025 at the EHMA Conference in Rennes. It lasted around 1,5 hours and combined presentations with interactive discussions. Coordinators and technical partners introduced the project, its outcomes, and the REBECCA Platform. Participants then engaged in a World Café-style discussion across tables representing different stakeholder groups, focusing on obstacles and enablers for system adoption. The session concluded with table representatives sharing key insights, overarching takeaways highlighted by the coordinators, and participants completing the External Expert System Evaluation Survey. A total of 17 participants attended, including a representative from an HTA (start-up), a representative from EUREGHA, policy managers, researchers, an interoperability architect, patients, students in health management, health managers, and nurses. The following summary captures key insights from the breakout discussions, highlighting valuable perspectives from several stakeholders.

7.1 Workshop's key insights

1. User-centric data approaches

The workshop stressed that digital health tools like REBECCA must start with real user and patient needs to ensure relevance, trust, and long-term engagement. Participants highlighted the importance of making data accessible not just for researchers and policymakers but also for patients and other stakeholders. Data should be presented in formats that are understandable and relatable, avoiding overly abstract or numerical presentations that could hinder engagement. Co-creation with users was seen as essential, with localised solutions reflecting individual contexts and experiences. Patients also emphasised that systems should feel rewarding over time to encourage continued use.

2. Trust, engagement, and human-centredness

Building trust was identified as foundational, requiring transparency, respect, and responsiveness from those who manage data. Clear, plain-language communication was seen as critical to making scientific and policy information accessible to all user groups, with attention to tone to foster inclusivity. Participants asked about translation practices used for REBECCA communications and stressed the need for culturally appropriate translations. Neutral intermediaries such as nurses and community facilitators were recognised as key in connecting users with digital systems. Social and

cultural sensitivity was also seen as crucial, especially when working with vulnerable groups.

3. Patient trust, data sensitivities, and involvement

Participants agreed that patients should be active co-creators rather than passive data sources, with their preferences and insights shaping the design and implementation of tools like REBECCA. Human-centred design should ensure patients feel respected, with empathy and personalisation at the core, particularly when using highly sensitive data such as social media history. Discussions highlighted the importance of consent and control, including the ability to opt out of certain data streams such as GPS or browsing history. A student nurse reflected that she would find such systems valuable in her future career and would recommend them to patients if trust and clarity were ensured.

4. Decentralisation and local engagement

Participants underlined that digital solutions should not follow a one-size-fits-all approach. They recommended decentralising system design and governance to better reflect local needs, practices, and capacities. Special emphasis was placed on reaching rural and underserved areas, with communication strategies tailored to settings with lower literacy levels or limited connectivity.

5. Demographics, equity, and accessibility

The workshop noted that system design must account for demographic differences such as age, health status, digital literacy, and rural residency. Data equity was highlighted as a priority, ensuring everyone has equal access to services and the ability to benefit from them. Particular care must be taken when handling sensitive data, such as social media and online behaviour, to ensure transparency, consent, and respect for privacy.

6. Translating expertise and bridging policy gaps

Participants highlighted the need to turn scientific insights into actionable and understandable information for policymakers, while involving them early in the project cycle. Political sensitivity and resistance were recognised as barriers that can be mitigated through participatory policymaking and inclusive dialogue. Sustaining engagement over time was also seen as important, supported by clear communication of benefits and strong usability.

7. Integration of science, policy, and healthcare

The workshop encouraged stronger links between research and patient care pathways, particularly when introducing innovation such as AI. The use of AI in primary care must be handled carefully, ensuring that patients understand the process and retain a sense

of control. Participants were curious about whether REBECCA would eventually transition into a standardised platform to support future scaling and implementation. Ethical and transparent governance was emphasised as vital for protecting patient safety, autonomy, and societal benefit.

In conclusion, the workshop highlighted a set of key action points to guide the development of digital health tools. These include translating scientific language for policymakers and patients, promoting human-centred and participatory design, and ensuring patients are trusted co-creators. Systems should enable decentralisation, account for demographic and social sensitivities, and communicate clearly and empathetically. Building scientific and data literacy, clarifying the benefits and optionality of data collection, and designing tools that remain valuable over time were emphasised. Finally, bridging research, policy, and practice while planning for long-term sustainability emerged as essential for meaningful, lasting impact.

7.2 Results of the External Expert System Evaluation

At the end of the workshop, participants were invited to complete the External Expert System Evaluation Survey (Annex B.3) to capture their perceptions and feedback regarding the REBECCA system. The following graph shows the distribution of the different stakeholder groups that filled in the evaluation.

Distribution of stakeholder groups

Figure 59. Distribution of stakeholder groups in the final workshop, n=15

The External Expert System Evaluation questionnaire collected information on stakeholders’ willingness to support integration of REBECCA, the perceived importance of integration within patient management and clinical research, and evaluations of the system’s innovativeness and practicality, using 7-point Likert scales (*From 1: Not at all to 7: Extremely*).

Figure 60. Average rating per stakeholder group, n=15

The evaluation results show generally positive perceptions of the REBECCA system across stakeholder groups, with some differences in emphasis. Willingness to support integration was high for all groups, highest among public health students and policy makers. The health professional rated the system as most important for patient management and clinical research, while researchers and students gave slightly lower scores. Perceptions of innovativeness varied, with health authorities rating it highest and students lowest. Practicality received more mixed evaluations, with health professionals expressing the most concerns. Overall, the results suggest broad acceptability of the system, but highlight the need to address practical implementation challenges, particularly for health professionals.

Conclusions

The internal evaluation of the REBECCA system across different countries, WPs, and participant groups provides valuable insights into its overall usability, satisfaction, and effectiveness in supporting patient care. Pragmatic quality scores were generally positive, particularly among HCPs and patients in the intervention studies (WP6), while hedonic quality scores were mostly neutral, with lower ratings from HC and BCS. In terms of usability, SUS scores were generally acceptable or marginally acceptable for all participant groups. Differences in reported QoL improvement, with Spanish patients showing the highest improvement, suggest that the system's impact may vary according to local context. The relatively low trust in data reported by Spanish HCPs further highlights a barrier to clinical adoption, emphasizing the need for improved data transparency and integration with existing workflows.

These findings were complemented by the External Expert System Evaluation conducted during the final stakeholder workshop. Results indicate broad acceptability of the REBECCA system among external stakeholders, while also highlighting practical implementation challenges, particularly for frontline health professionals. The workshop also identified key action points for digital health tool development, including human-centred and participatory design, patient involvement as trusted co-creators, clear and empathetic communication, decentralisation, consideration of demographic and social sensitivities, promotion of data literacy, and long-term sustainability.

Taken together, these insights suggest that while the REBECCA system demonstrates usability and functional adequacy, future development should focus on enhancing engagement, building trust, and supporting adaptation to local contexts. Integrating the workshop recommendations will further maximise the system's value and facilitate successful adoption in real-world settings.

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ANNEX

A. Evaluation forms

A.1 Evaluation form – Patients

Confidential *Page 1*

WP6P_Evaluation

Welcome to the Rebecca System evaluation form!

Your feedback is very valuable to us.

Thank you for taking the time to answer the form and help us improve.

Let's get started!

Participant_ID _____

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Page 2

We now want to ask you some questions about the REBECCA app.

Please rate the REBECCA app.

(User Experience Questionnaire)

The REBECCA app is: Obstructive Supportive

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Complicated Easy

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Inefficient Efficient

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Confusing Clear

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Boring Exciting

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Not interesting Interesting

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Conventional Inventive

(Place a mark on the scale above)

The REBECCA app is: Usual Leading edge

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Confidential

Page 3

Please rate the following statements about the REBBECA app.

(System Usability Scale)

I think that I would like to use this system frequently.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I found the system unnecessarily complex.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I thought the system was easy to use.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I found the system very cumbersome to use.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I felt very confident using the system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

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Page 4

Please answer the following questions about the REBECCA app.

(Additional questions)

The system was user-friendly and enjoyable to use Strongly Agree ---------- Strongly disagree
(Place a mark on the scale above)

Were the instructions provided clear and easy to understand and follow? Yes No

Do you feel that the REBECCA app enhanced your quality of life after your primary treatment? Yes No

To what extent did it improve your quality of life? A little Moderately A lot Extremely

Based on your experience as a participant in REBECCA, would you mind providing this type of data, in other contexts in the future? Yes No Not sure

Do you think it would be good if all patients in the future could be followed up in this way? Yes No Not sure

If no, what do you think should be changed/is missing?

Has the use of the REBECCA system made you more worried or stressed about your health? Yes No Not sure

How secure do you feel about the privacy and confidentiality of your data while using the REBECCA app? Very Insecure Insecure I do not know Secure Very Secure

The future is becoming more and more digital and the REBECCA project is future-oriented in this respect. We are therefore wondering what you think about sharing this type of data (smartwatch and GPS data)? Okay Not okay Haven't thought about it

If not okay, what should be changed so that you think it is okay to share data?

Have you felt monitored with regard to the data collection? Yes No Haven't thought about it

If yes, is the collection of GPS contributing to your feeling of surveillance? Yes No Not sure

Have you provided location (GPS) data to the project? Yes No

If no, why not? I didn't want to The battery on the mobile got worse and I had to charge the phone more often

Confidential

Page 5

Do you think it has taken a lot of time to be a participant in the REBECCA project? Yes No

What has taken a lot of time? _____

If REBECCA's PC plug-in for collecting data related to your internet activity had been available for tablets and/or mobile phones, would you have wanted to use it? Yes No Not sure

How would you rate your overall satisfaction with your experience using the REBECCA system? Very satisfied Not satisfied at all
_____ (Place a mark on the scale above)

Would you have used the REBECCA system longer if you had the opportunity? Yes No Not sure

Please list three aspects of the system that you liked and three aspects that you believe need improvement or modification. _____

Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for enhancing the system further? _____

A.2 Evaluation form – BCS (Sweden Feasibility study)

Feedback

Välkommen till Rebecca-systemets utvärderingsformulär!

Din feedback är mycket värdefull för oss.

Tack för att du tar dig tid att svara på formuläret och hjälpa oss att bli bättre.

Låt oss börja!

Page 1

Vi vill nu ställa några frågor om REBECCA appen.

Vänligen utvärdera REBECCA appen.

(Frågeformulär för användarupplevelse)

REBECCA appen är:	Hindrande	Stödjande	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Komplicerad	Enkel	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Ineffektiv	Effektiv	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Förvirrande	Tydlig	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Tråkig	Spännande	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Ointressant	Intressant	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Konventionell	Innovativ	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>
REBECCA appen är:	Vanlig	I framkant	<p style="font-size: small; margin-top: 2px;">(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>

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Vänligen utvärdera följande påståenden om REBECCA appen.

(Systemanvändbarhetsskala)

<p>Jag skulle vilja använda det här systemet ofta.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag tyckte att systemet var onödigt komplicerat.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag tyckte att systemet var lätt att använda.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag skulle behöva stöd av en teknisk person för att kunna använda det här systemet.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag tyckte att de olika funktionerna i systemet var väl integrerade.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag tyckte att det här systemet var för inkonsekvent.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag kan tänka mig att de flesta skulle lära sig att använda det här systemet väldigt snabbt.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag tyckte att systemet var väldigt krångligt att använda.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag kände mig väldigt säker på att använda systemet.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		
<p>Jag behövde lära mig flera saker innan jag kunde komma igång med att använda det här systemet.</p>	<p>Instämmer helt</p>	<p>Instämmer inte alls</p>
<p>-----</p> <p>(Place a mark on the scale above)</p>		

Vänligen svara på följande frågor om REBECCA appen.
(Tillägsfrågor)

Systemet var användarvänligt och trevligt att använda.

Instämmer helt

Instämmer inte
alls

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Var instruktionerna tydliga och lätta att förstå och följa?

Instämmer helt

Instämmer inte
alls

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Baserat på din erfarenhet som deltagare i REBECCA, skulle du ha något emot att dela med dig av samma typ av data, i andra sammanhang i framtiden?

Ja Nej Vet inte

Tror du att det vore bra om alla patienter i framtiden kunde följas upp på det här sättet?

Ja Nej Vet inte

Om nej, vad tycker du borde ändras/saknas?

Har användningen av REBECCA-systemet gjort dig mer orolig eller stressad över din hälsa?

Ja Nej Vet inte

Hur säker känner du dig gällande integriteten och sekretessen för dina uppgifter när du använder REBECCA-appen?

Mycket osäker
 Osäker
 Jag vet inte
 Säker
 Mycket säker

Framtiden blir mer och mer digital och REBECCA-projektet är framtidsinriktat i detta avseende. Vi undrar därför vad du tycker om att dela den här typen av data (smartklocka och GPS-data)?

Okej Inte okej Har inte tänkt på det

Om inte okej, vad behöver ändras för att du ska känna att det är okej att dela den typen av data?

Har du känt dig övervakad när det gäller datainsamlingen?

Ja Nej Har inte tänkt på det

Om ja, bidrar insamlingen av GPS-data till din känsla av övervakning?

Ja Nej Vet inte

Har du tillhandahållit platsdata (GPS) till projektet?

Ja Nej

Om nej, varför inte?

Jag ville inte Batteriet på mobilen blev sämre och jag fick ladda telefonen oftare

Tycker du att det har tagit mycket tid att vara deltagare i REBECCA-projektet? Ja Nej

Vad har tagit mycket tid?

Om insamlingen av data relaterad till din internetaktivitet hade varit tillgänglig även för surfplattor och/eller mobiltelefoner, hade du varit villig att dela med dig av denna information också? Ja Nej Vet inte

Hur skulle du bedöma din totala tillfredsställelse med din erfarenhet av att använda REBECCA-systemet? Väldigt nöjd Väldigt missnöjd

.....

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Skulle du ha använt REBECCA-systemet längre om du haft möjlighet? Ja Nej Vet inte

Vänligen ange tre aspekter av systemet som du gillade och tre aspekter som du anser behöver förbättras eller modifieras.

Har du några andra kommentarer eller förslag för att förbättra systemet ytterligare?

Frågor angående livsstilskonsultationen

Hur mycket litar du på vägledningen från konsultationen baserat på data som samlats in i REBECCA-appen?

- Inte alls
 Lite
 Måttligt
 Mycket
 Helt och hållet

Stämde rekommendationerna överens med dina behov?

- Inte alls
 Lite
 Måttligt
 Mycket
 Helt och hållet

Upplever du att konsultationen baserad på din data förbättrade din livskvalitet?

- Ja
 Nej

I vilken utsträckning förbättrade den din livskvalitet?

- Lite
 Måttligt
 Mycket
 Helt och hållet

A.3 Evaluation form - HCP

Confidential Page 1

WP6HCP_Evaluation

Welcome to the Rebecca System evaluation form!
Your feedback is very valuable to us.
Thank you for taking the time to answer the form and help us improve.
Let's get started!

Participant_id _____

13/02/2025 10:53 projectredcap.org

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Please rate the following statements about the REBBECA system.

(System Usability Scale)

I think that I would like to use this system frequently.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I found the system unnecessarily complex.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I thought the system was easy to use.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I found the system very cumbersome to use.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I felt very confident using the system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.

Strongly Agree Strongly disagree

(Place a mark on the scale above)

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Please answer the following questions about the REBECCA system.

(Additional questions)

Do you feel that the REBECCA system was integrated into your clinical workflow? Yes No

To what extent the REBECCA system was integrated into your clinical workflow? A little Moderately A lot Extremely

Do you feel that the clinical dashboard was useful in improving your workflow? Yes No

To what extent did it improve your workflow? A little Moderately A lot Extremely

How much do you trust the information and data provided by the REBECCA app in monitoring patients' lifestyles? Not at all A little Moderately A lot Extremely

Were there any concerns regarding data security? Yes No

Were the training and support resources for using the REBECCA system sufficient? Yes No

Did you receive assistance when encountering issues with the system? Yes No

How would you rate your overall satisfaction with your experience using the REBECCA system? Very satisfied Not satisfied at all

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Please list three aspects of the system that you liked and three aspects that you believe need improvement or modification. _____

Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for enhancing the system further? _____

B. REBECCA final stakeholder workshop

B.1 Workshop's structure

Duration: 1 hour 15 minutes

Objectives:

- Evaluate and validate the REBECCA system's acceptance by patients and health professionals.
- Support exploitation strategies and sustainability planning.
- Discuss integration of RWD-based solutions into healthcare systems and clinical workflows.
- Engage stakeholders to explore adoption strategies and implementation pathways.

Workshop Structure:

1. Introduction (15 minutes)

- Project presentation and main outcomes by the coordinators.
- Platform introduction by the technical partners.

2. Interactive Discussion – World Café Technique (35 minutes)

- Participants rotated across three tables, each representing a stakeholder group: decision-makers/policymakers, health authorities/regulatory bodies, health professionals/managers, researchers/tech innovators, and patients' organisations.
- Each table was provided with key discussion topics focusing on obstacles and enablers for adopting the REBECCA system in their respective work.
- Each table nominated a representative to remain at the table and present its key insights at the end of the session.

3. Takeaways & Conclusions (25 minutes)

- Table representatives shared their discussion outcomes.
- Coordinators highlighted overarching takeaways and final remarks.
- Participants were invited to complete the External Expert System Evaluation Survey, available via QR code or paper copy.

Expected Outcomes:

- Gather concrete insights and recommendations for large-scale deployment of the REBECCA system.
- Create a roadmap for integrating the system into stakeholders' workflows.
- Collect evaluation data via the External Expert System Evaluation Survey.

B.2 Workshops notes

REBECCA workshop at EHMA conference – summary of key insights on health data (5th June 2025, in Rennes)

The REBECCA workshop explored the challenges and opportunities surrounding the use of health data, particularly personal data, with a strong focus on ethical, inclusive, and user-centred approaches. This summary includes collective reflections from breakout discussions, including valuable patient and practitioner perspectives.

Workshop with:

17 participants.

- Representant from an HTA company (start-up)
- Representant from EUREGHA
- Policy manager
- Interoperability architect
- Patients
- Students in health management
- Health managers
- Nurse

1. User-centric data approaches

- Start with user needs: the workshop emphasised the importance of grounding digital health tools like REBECCA in real user and patient needs to ensure relevance, trust, and long-term engagement.
- Data accessibility for all: data should not only serve researchers and policymakers. Participants advocated for meaningful, secure, and broader data access to empower all stakeholders, especially patients.
- Making data personal: data should be presented in formats that are relatable and understandable to users. Abstract or purely numerical forms may hinder understanding and engagement.

- User co-creation: emphasis was placed on involving users in co-creating localised solutions that reflect individual contexts, lifestyles, and healthcare experiences.
- Rewarding experience: a key patient-side insight was the importance of designing systems that feel rewarding over time, encouraging sustained use and engagement.

2. Trust, engagement, and human-centredness

- Trust is foundational: building trust in the system and in those who manage data is essential. Participants discussed how trust must be earned through transparency, respect, and responsiveness.
- Clear communication: scientific and policy-related language must be translated into plain, accessible terms to reach and resonate with all user groups. The *tone* of communication is also critical to foster trust and inclusiveness.
- Language translation practices: participants asked what resources were used in the translation process of REBECCA communications and highlighted the importance of culturally appropriate translation and tone.
- Role of intermediaries: neutral actors such as nurses, community facilitators, and healthcare professionals play a critical role in bridging the gap between users and digital systems.
- Social and cultural sensitivity: effective engagement with patients and communities requires recognition of emotional, social, and cultural factors surrounding data use, especially concerning vulnerable groups.

3. Patient trust, data sensitivities, and involvement

- Active participation, not passive use: patients must be seen as co-creators, not just data sources. Their insights and preferences must shape the design and implementation of digital health tools.
- Empathy and personalisation: human-centred design should ensure patients feel respected and seen as individuals. This was particularly relevant when discussing the use of highly sensitive data (e.g., social media history).
- Consent and control: there was a lively discussion around the type of personal data collected (e.g., GPS, browsing history) and whether patients can opt out of certain data streams. Optionality and informed consent are seen as critical.

- Student nurse perspective: a participant in training shared how REBECCA-type systems would be highly useful in her future career and that she would be comfortable recommending it to patients, provided trust and clarity are ensured.

4. Decentralisation and local engagement

- Local-level design: solutions should not be one-size-fits-all. Participants stressed the need to decentralise system design and governance to align with local needs, practices, and capabilities.
- Reaching rural and underserved areas: specific attention was drawn to oral-level communication and engagement strategies that work in non-urban, low-literacy, or lower-connectivity settings.

5. Demographics, equity, and accessibility

- Tailored approaches: demographic factors such as age, digital literacy, rural residency, and health status must be actively considered when designing systems.
- Data equity: it is crucial that all individuals, regardless of background, have equal access to data-driven services and are equipped to understand and benefit from them.
- Sensitive data handling: data types like social media or online behaviour were flagged as particularly sensitive. Ensuring transparency, consent, and respect in their use is key.

6. Translating expertise and bridging policy gaps

- Science–policy communication: there is a strong need to convert scientific insights into actionable, understandable language for policymakers. Policymakers should be included early in the data project cycle.
- Overcoming political barriers: political sensitivity and resistance can pose major challenges. Participatory policymaking and inclusive dialogue are seen as strategic tools to mitigate these issues.
- Engagement over time: participants discussed how to sustain user engagement over time – highlighting the importance of clear benefit communication and system usability.

7. Integration of science, policy, and healthcare

- Bridging R&D and care pathways: the workshop encouraged better integration between research and patient care processes, particularly in the context of innovation (e.g., AI).
- AI in primary care: artificial intelligence in general practitioner workflows must be introduced with caution and care, ensuring patients understand and feel in control of the process.
- Future scalability: participants were curious whether REBECCA plans to migrate toward a standardised platform to support broader future implementation and exploitation.
- Ethical and transparent governance: all processes should be grounded in ethical standards and transparency to support patient safety, autonomy, and societal benefit.

Summary of key action points

1. Translate scientific language for policymakers and patients.
2. Promote human-centred and participatory design.
3. Ensure patient trust and agency – make patients co-creators.
4. Enable decentralisation and local-level adaptation.
5. Consider demographic and social sensitivities.
6. Communicate clearly and with empathy – in tone and content.
7. Build scientific and data literacy to support engagement.
8. Clarify benefits and optionality of data collection.
9. Design systems to be rewarding and valuable over time.
10. Bridge R&D, policy, and practice – plan for long-term sustainability.

B.3 REBECCA Final Stakeholder Workshop Questionnaire

REBECCA Final Stakeholder Workshop Questionnaire**1. Please indicate in which stakeholder group you belong to:**

- Decision/Policy - makers
- Health authorities and regulatory bodies
- Health professionals and health managers
- Researchers and tech innovators
- Patients' organisations

2. How willing would you be to support the integration of a system such as REBECCA within your expert domain? From 1: Not at all to 7: Extremely

- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. How important is the integration of a system like REBECCA within the current patient management system? From 1: Not at all to 7: Extremely

- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

4. How important is the integration of a system like REBECCA within the current clinical research domain? From 1: Not at all to 7: Extremely

- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

5. How would you evaluate the innovativeness of the REBECCA system? From 1: Not innovative at all to 7: Extremely innovative

- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7

6. How would you evaluate the practicality of the REBECCA system? From 1: Not practical at all to 7: Extremely practical

- 1 2 3 4 5 6 7